

Environmental and Cybersecurity Challenges in the Baltic Sea Shipping

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Abstract

The maritime sector faces several challenges that include for instance, the environmental impact of ports and shipping, including greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions and cyber resilience. This study addresses these topics and has raised the following research questions: 1) How do inconsistencies in GHG emissions calculation methodologies across Baltic Sea ports affect the monitoring and reduction of emissions, and what standardised methodologies can be developed to address these inconsistencies? 2) What are the key cybersecurity requirements identified for port digital solutions, and how can a risk matrix be utilised to develop mitigating strategies for these threats? 3) What are the main shipping-related pollution categories that affect the environment focusing on the Estonian sea area? The sector must address inconsistencies in GHG emissions calculations across Baltic Sea ports. Different methodologies lead to incomparable results, hindering effective monitoring and reduction strategies [1]. Standardised GHG emission mapping methodologies, incorporating clear guidelines on emission categories and preferred methodologies, are vital for meaningful comparisons and global and regional emission reduction efforts. Cyber resilience is crucial for shipping companies to protect their assets from sophisticated cyberattacks. Effective strategies and mitigation methods, such as incident response plans, secure backup strategies, and regular staff training, are essential. The study that has been carried out identified 23 cybersecurity requirements for port digital solutions, highlighting main threats like data breaches, denial of service, and ransomware. Based on the example tool, it was possible to build a risk matrix and provide a mitigating strategy while adapting new solutions in the port area. The environmental impact of shipping activities in the Estonian Sea area, as one of the countries that surround the Baltic Sea, requires a standardised assessment approach. Pollution categories include discharges to water, air emissions, and physical pollution, with noise identified as having the highest impact [2].

Implications for sustainable maritime operation

By addressing cyber resilience, standardising GHG emission methodologies, and assessing environmental impacts, the maritime sector can enhance its sustainability and resilience. These efforts will not only benefit the maritime industry but also serve as a model for other sectors seeking to address climate change and cybersecurity challenges.